

Narrow Linewidth Ridge Waveguide AlGaAs Diode Lasers with Surface Gratings

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Motivation

- Gratings integrated in AlGaAs laser diodes for defined wavelengths with
 - reduced thermal shift due to self-heating
 - narrow linewidths: ridge waveguide DFB < 10 MHz; DBR < 200 kHz
- Laser sources in optical systems for various applications, e.g.
 - sensing (LIDAR, OCT)
 - spectroscopy (Raman)
 - imaging (digital holography)
 - metrology (optical clocks)

Realisation of Surface Gratings

- Ebeam lithography of high-order gratings with gratings slits 100 ... 200 nm and periods > 450 nm
- Ti/nLOF (50 nm/ 800 nm) hardmask structured with RIE (SF₆/O)
- In-situ control of the RIE process
- Up to 1.5 µm deep grooves into AlGaAs with RIE (BCl₃; Ar)

Grating fabrication process with three etch steps and etch rate factor

SEM X-Section grating grooves with different depths

Grating grooves and resist for RW definition

FIB milled side view of 2.2 µm RW with 1.27 µm deep SG grooves

Simulations of grating reflectivity

- Statistics over a large number of samples → accuracy of etch depths ± 50 nm
- Functional high order gratings require grating grooves
 - with precise etch depth
 - with V-shaped profile to setup a high duty-cycle

Device Examples

- Surface gratings have been applied for various types of AlGaAs diode lasers. Two recent examples →

4-wavelength DBR array around 667 nm

- 10th order gratings with four different periods

- Controlled wavelength spreading of the four DBR lasers on the array is below 100 pm (same current)

Monolithically integrated external cavity diode laser (mECDL) at 1064 nm

- Long, low-loss monolithically integrated cavity with gratings as back reflector

- Measured 3 dB linewidth of 25 kHz (homodyning) is the smallest reported linewidth of a monolithically integrated diode lasers

At FBH, surface gratings are routinely used to produce medium quantities of high-performance wavelength-stabilized lasers.